

“Exposure Assessment in Cadmium”

ImproRisk Scientific Report

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1 Summary

Cadmium occurs naturally in the environment in its inorganic form, and anthropogenic sources have further contributed to background levels of cadmium in soil, water and living organisms. The general population is exposed to cadmium from multiple sources, including smoking, but in the non-smoking general population food is the dominant source. Cadmium is primarily toxic to the kidney, but can also cause bone demineralisation and has been statistically associated with increased risk of cancer in the lung, endometrium, bladder, and breast. In the current report the dietary exposure of the target population is studied using ImproRisk model v.0.3.2. The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary cadmium intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the Tolerable Weekly Intake (TWI) of 2.5 µg/kg body weight (b.w.) per week and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary cadmium exposure.

Mean dietary Cadmium exposure of the Cypriot population was calculated as 0.884 and 2.471 µg/kg b.w. per week for mean and high consumers, respectively. It was found that approximately 5 % of the whole population was exposed over the TWI value of 2.5 µg/Kg b.w. per week. Much higher exposure was observed for infants, toddlers and other children due to their lower body weight and may be from the consumption habits.

There was no significant difference in Cadmium intake between genders and different geographical areas.

Squids, cuttlefishes, octopuses (20.4%), potatoes (17.9%), tomatoes (7.4%), pasta (5.2%), chocolate and chocolate products (5.0%) and cereal flakes (4.7%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to Cadmium intake.

2 Introduction

Cadmium occurs naturally in the environment in its inorganic form as a result of volcanic emissions and weathering of rocks. In addition, anthropogenic sources have increased the background levels of cadmium in soil, water and living organisms. Cadmium is released into the environment by wastewater and waste incineration. Contamination of agricultural soils can occur by the use of fertilisers, by air deposition and by cadmium containing sewage sludge. Increases in cadmium levels in soil result in an increase in the uptake of cadmium by plants, depending on plant species, pH and other characteristics of the soil, and thus indirectly by animals feeding on the plants. Cadmium in water can contaminate shellfish and crustaceans. Fungi that are natural accumulators of cadmium can receive high levels from soil.

The general population is exposed to cadmium from multiple sources, including smoking, with food accounting for approximately 90 % of cadmium exposure in the non-smoking general population. Less than 10 % of total exposure of the non-smoking general population occurs due to inhalation of low levels of cadmium in ambient air and through drinking water.

Cadmium absorption after dietary exposure in humans is relatively low (3–5 %), but cadmium is efficiently retained in the kidney and liver, with a very long biological half-life ranging from 10 to 30 years. Cadmium is primarily toxic to the kidney, especially to the proximal tubular cells where it accumulates over time and may cause a decrease in the glomerular filtration rate, and eventually renal failure. Cadmium can also cause bone demineralisation, either through direct bone damage or indirectly as a result of renal dysfunction. The International Agency for Research on Cancer has classified cadmium as a human carcinogen (Group 1) on the basis of occupational studies (IARC, 1993). Newer data on human exposure to cadmium in the general population have been statistically associated with increased risk of cancer in the lung, endometrium, bladder, and breast.

In 2009 and subsequently confirmed in 2011, the Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain issued an opinion in which they recommended that the PTWI should be reduced to a tolerable weekly intake (TWI) of 2.5 µg/kg b.w. in order to ensure a high level of protection of consumers, including subgroups of the population such as children, vegetarians or people living in highly contaminated areas.

2.1 Background

2.2 Terms of Reference

The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary cadmium intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the Tolerable Weekly Intake (TWI) of 2.5 µg/kg body weight (b.w.) per week and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary cadmium exposure.

3 Data and Methodology

3.1 Occurrence data

Cadmium occurrence data in food were extracted from LIMS for the years 2008-2020. For results below LOD, EFSA's assumption was applied. Occurrence results below the LOD were set to zero for the Low-bound scenario, half the LOD for the Middle-bound scenario and LOD for the Upper-bound scenario. Dilution factors were applied in order to estimate concentrations for different coffee and cocoa beverages, tea beverages and liquid children and infant milk. The aggregated occurrence dataset contained 313 food items.

3.2 Consumption data

Food consumption data were obtained from the EUMenu project funded by EFSA and the dietary survey was carried out in the years 2014-2018. The consumption data was the result of a survey of 1661 participants (male and female). The survey covered all five cities of Cyprus, rural and urban regions, and also all days of the week and the four seasons. The population classes and the number of participants in each class were: [a] infants: 3-11 months (269), [b] toddlers: 12-35 months (279), [c] other children: 3-9 years (300), [d] adolescents: 10-17 years (274), [e] adults: 18-64 years (275) and [f] elderly: 65-74 years (264). The consumption dataset contained 82921 occasions.

3.3 Food classification

Consumption and occurrence data were both codified according to the FoodEx2 classification system developed by EFSA. At the moment of the generation of the present report the MTX catalogue version 13.1 was applied.

3.4 Methodologies

3.4.1 Chronic dietary exposure

Dietary exposure was assessed at individual level by multiplying the average daily consumption of each food with the corresponding mean occurrence estimated for Cadmium summing up the respective intakes throughout the diet and finally dividing the results by the individual's body weight.

3.4.2 Dietary exposure assessment model

Dietary exposure assessment was performed using ImproRisk model version 0.3.2

4 Dietary Exposure Assessment

Table 4.1 presents the substance information.

Table 4.1: Substance information

key	
Chemical Substance	Cadmium
Substance Category	Contaminant
Reference value	2.5 µg/Kg b.w. per week
Type of reference value	Tolerable Weekly Intake (TWI)

Table 4.2 presents the exposure statistics.

Table 4.2: Summary exposure statistics of Cadmium

Scenario			
key	LB (µg/Kg b.w. per week)	MB (µg/Kg b.w. per week)	UB (µg/Kg b.w. per week)
Min	0.032	0.068	0.104
Max	27.161	27.196	27.231
Mean	0.81	0.884	0.957
SD	1.194	1.206	1.221
P25	0.314	0.366	0.419
Median	0.527	0.587	0.653
P75	0.817	0.891	0.985
P95	2.366	2.471	2.585
pctOver	4.3%	4.9%	5.7%

* pctOver:Percentage of population above the reference value

Mean and 95th percentile exposure were calculated as 0.884 and 2.471 µg/kg b.w. per week (Table 4.2). It was found that approximately 5 % of the whole population was exposed over the TWI value of 2.5 µg/Kg b.w. per week, as also shown in Figures 4.1 and 4.2.

4.1 Distribution of exposure

Probability distribution

Figure 4.1 shows the probability distribution of the exposure.

Figure 4.1: Probability distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

Cumulative distribution

Figure 4.2 shows the cumulative distribution of exposure.

Figure 4.2: Cumulative distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

4.2 Mean Exposure at the MB by Gender

Table 4.3: Summary exposure statistics Gender at MB scenario.

Gender	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
FEMALE	0.086	13.654	0.83	1.043	0.342	0.569	0.875	2.446	4.7%
MALE	0.068	27.196	0.94	1.354	0.393	0.608	0.912	2.588	5.2%

Table 4.3 and Figure 4.3 shows that there is no significant difference between the two genders meaning same food consumption habits for male and female subjects.

Figure 4.3: Mean Exposure by Gender at MB scenario.

4.3 Mean Exposure at the MB by Area

Table 4.4: Summary exposure statistics by Area at MB scenario.

Area	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Ammochostos	0.086	27.196	0.850	1.964	0.339	0.482	0.827	1.950	2.8%
Larnaka	0.108	12.762	0.644	0.675	0.326	0.491	0.745	1.625	1.7%
Lefkosia	0.068	10.156	1.019	1.345	0.362	0.649	1.044	3.130	6.1%
Lemesos	0.094	13.654	0.912	1.056	0.468	0.640	0.931	2.533	6.1%
Pafos	0.142	11.100	0.890	1.161	0.376	0.598	0.859	4.163	6.1%

Figure 4.4: Mean Exposure by Area at MB scenario.

4.4 Mean Exposure at the MB by Population Class

Table 4.5: Summary exposure statistics by Population Class at MB scenario.

Population class	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Adolescents	0.152	27.196	1.247	1.990	0.585	0.841	1.306	2.867	6%
Adults	0.068	9.792	0.733	0.970	0.343	0.529	0.740	1.626	3.7%
Elderly	0.086	13.654	0.662	1.212	0.277	0.439	0.632	1.325	2.7%
Infants	0.291	4.233	1.263	0.777	0.717	1.048	1.707	2.847	9%
Other children	0.184	12.762	1.705	1.389	0.966	1.382	1.952	3.590	14.5%
Toddlers	0.355	9.527	1.652	0.952	1.106	1.482	1.930	3.287	11.3%

In Table 4.5 and Figure 4.5 the exposure of each population class is shown. It was found that toddlers and other children had the highest exposure, followed by infants and adolescents showing two or three times higher exposure than adults and elderly. The lower body weight of these population classes is a reason for the higher exposure. Also 14.5% of other children, 11.3% of toddlers and 9% of the infants were exceeding the TWI for cadmium intake. Investigating the consumption data it was observed that infants mainly consume infant formula, cereal baby food, potatoes, rice and other vegetables, food with relatively low cadmium concentrations, in amounts that due to their very low body weight will lead to high cadmium intake. On the other hand, other children and toddlers were more exposed to

cadmium and a higher percentage exceeded the TWI, because in some cases high amounts of squids and other molluscs were consumed in these population classes.

Figure 4.5: Mean Exposure by Population Class at MB scenario.

4.5 Mean Exposure at the MB scenario by [Area and Population class]

Figure 4.6 illustrates the mean exposure to cadmium by population class and geographical area. It was found that there is no significant difference between the geographical areas in all population classes. The exposure seems to be independent of the geographical area. This is because the population in Cyprus has the same food consumption habits and the foodstuffs that are contaminated by cadmium are consumed by all population classes.

Mean Cadmium exposure (MB scenario)

Across Area and Population class

Figure 4.6: Cross Plot

4.6 Contributions of different food groups to the dietary exposure

The contribution of each main food group to the total cadmium exposure is shown in Figure 4.7. Squids, cuttlefishes, octopuses (20.4%), potatoes (17.9%), tomatoes (7.4%), pasta (5.2%), chocolate and chocolate products (5.0%) and cereal flakes (4.7%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the cadmium intake. Although, potatoes, tomatoes and cereal flakes had relatively low cadmium concentration, they are highly consumed by all population classes. On the other hand molluscs and cocoa and cocoa products (chocolate) are lower consumed by the population, but are highly contaminated with cadmium.

Figure 4.7 shows the contribution of food items at FoodEx Level 3

Figure 4.7: Contribution to the Cadmium Total Exposure MB.

Table 4.6: Contribution to the Cadmium Total Exposure (MB). Food items at FoodEx2 Level 3 with greater than 1% contribution

Level1	Level2	Level3	Contribution
Grains and grain-based products	Cereals and cereal primary derivatives	Cereal grains (and cereal-like grains)	1.79%

Level1	Level2	Level3	Contribution
Grains and grain-based products	Cereals and cereal primary derivatives	Cereal and cereal-like flours	1.14%
Grains and grain-based products	Fine bakery wares	Biscuits	2.15%
Grains and grain-based products	Fine bakery wares	Cakes	1.13%
Grains and grain-based products	Fine bakery wares	Yeast leavened pastry	1.83%
Grains and grain-based products	Breakfast cereals	Processed and mixed breakfast cereals	4.71%
Grains and grain-based products	Pasta, doughs and similar products	Pasta and similar products	5.24%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Fruiting vegetables	Solanacea	7.41%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Leafy vegetables	Lettuces and salad plants	2.06%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Leafy vegetables	Spinach-type leaves	1.56%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Herbs and edible flowers	Aromatic herbs	1.20%
Starchy roots or tubers and products thereof, sugar plants	Starchy roots and tubers	Potatoes and similar-	17.93%
Meat and meat products	Mammals and birds meat	Mammals meat	1.34%
Meat and meat products	Mammals and birds meat	Birds meat	1.29%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Molluscs	Squids, cuttlefishes, octopuses	20.40%
Milk and dairy products	Milk, whey and cream	Milk	2.07%
Sugar and similar, confectionery and water-based sweet desserts	Confectionery including chocolate	Chocolate and chocolate products	5.00%
Coffee, cocoa, tea and infusions	Ingredients for coffee, cocoa, tea, and herbal infusions	Cocoa ingredients	1.66%

Level1	Level2	Level3	Contribution
Coffee, cocoa, tea and infusions	Ingredients for coffee, cocoa, tea, and herbal infusions	Hot drinks and infusions composite ingredients	1.37%

5 Uncertainties

The evaluation of the uncertainties in the exposure assessment of Cadmium has been performed following the guidance of the Opinion of the Scientific Committee related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. Table 5.1 presents a summary of uncertainties, highlighting the main sources of uncertainty and providing an estimate whether each source of uncertainty is likely to lead to an over- or under-estimation of the calculated dietary exposure.

Table 5.1: Summary of qualitative evaluation of the impact of uncertainties on the dietary exposure to Cadmium.

Sources of uncertainty	Direction ¹
Different time frame between concentration data and consumption data	+/-
Long-term (chronic) exposure assessed from few days of consumption	+
Measurement error in amounts of food consumed	+/-
Measurement error in individual body weights	+/-
Assumptions taken into account for the preparation of occurrence data	+/-
Level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy for the calculation of the exposure	+

¹ + = uncertainty with potential to cause over-estimation of exposure; - = uncertainty with potential to cause under-estimation of exposure

A number of uncertainties can be identified regarding the selection of parameters, such as Cadmium concentration levels in foodstuffs and consumption data.

The uncertainty related to the representativeness of the occurrence data for certain food commodities with respect to the number of samples is taken into account. Given the fact that the analytical results were generated with an ICP-MS method in an accredited laboratory, this adds only slightly to the uncertainty of the analytical results.

Some potentially important extrapolation uncertainties arise since an individual survey of food consumption is used to estimate dietary exposure over a timescale longer than the

survey duration. Remaining uncertainties relate to the measurement error in amounts of consumed foodstuffs and individual body weights.

In ImproRisk occurrence and consumption data matching for the calculation of the exposure is performed based on a level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy, which may lead to overestimation of the exposure.

Furthermore, several assumption taken into account in the preparation of the occurrence data (data from EFSA, dilution factors, aggregation) may lead to some uncertainties.

6 Conclusions

Mean dietary Cadmium exposure of the Cypriot population was calculated as 0.884 and 2.471 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ b.w. per week for mean and high consumers, respectively. It was found that approximately 5 % of the whole population was exposed over the TWI value of 2.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ b.w. per week. Much higher exposure was observed for infants, toddlers and other children due to their lower body weight and may be from the consumption habits.

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7 References

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3. EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), 2006. Guidance of the Scientific Committee on a request from EFSA related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. The EFSA Journal. 438, 1-54.
4. EFSA. 2018. Internal report on the harmonisation of dilution factors to be used in the assessment of dietary exposure.

8 Abbreviations

Table 8.1: Abbreviations

Key	Description
BMDL	Benchmark dose lower limit (lower bound of benchmark dose interval)
b.w.	Body weight
LB	Lower bound
LOD	Limit of detection
MB	Middle bound
MoE	Margin of exposure
SD	Standard deviation
P25	25th percentile
P75	75th percentile
P95	95th percentile
UB	Upper bound
wcoeff	Weight coefficient

9 Appendices